

PSYCHOLOGY

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG DIFFERENTLY ABLE EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT: Emotional intelligence (EQ) plays a vital role in psychological and social adjustment of individuals. Present study was designed to make analysis of the facet of EQ in the context of differently able employees. The main objectives of this study include measuring EQ level of differently able employees, investigating the role of employees' demographic variations in age, education, experience and income while determining their EQ index. The BarOn Emotional Inventory was used to measure the EQ. It has 133 items and 5 subscales named as Interpersonal skills, Intrapersonal skills, Stress control, Adoptability and General mood and manner. A simple random sample of 50 employees was taken from Government and public sectors. Among them 39 were male and 11 were female, whose age ranged from 25 to 50 years. Findings revealed that younger employees have higher EQ as compared to elder employees. It was also revealed that professionally educated employees have lower emotional intelligence compared to other categories.

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Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the potential to understand and manage ones emotions in positive ways in a challenge situation and solve problem. In daily life, EI impacts different aspects of communication and interaction. Goleman (1995) implicated that self-awareness, selfcontrol, social awareness, social skills and self – regulating are the elements of EI and he argued that self- awareness is a basic element all other elements of emotional intelligence. He has viewed that individuals should care for Emotional Intelligence in order to excel in life challenges. As individuals' success and the success of the profession depend on ability to read other people's signals and react appropriately to them. Therefore, each one of us must develop the mature emotional intelligence skills required to better understand, empathize and negotiate with other people particularly as the economy has become more global. Otherwise, success will get away from lives and careers.

The employees are those who cannot perform their daily business pursue their emotional and social adjustment and comprehend their work and development needs because of their impairments in their physical organs. These employees need special care, deference and work efforts from their co-workers, family members and society are known as physically handicapped employees. These employees are different from normal employees because of their physical impairment. In terms of normal development and adjustment their disability proves too costly to them.

Disability

According to the Malaysian Persons with Disabilities Act of 2008 (Act 685), persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in society. If an individual is unable to perform major life activities including caring for oneself, walking, seeing, hearing, speaking, breathing or learning, to the extent of the average person, that individual is considered as an individual with disability. In addition, persons with disabilities include individuals who were disabled in the past or who are considered to be disabled by some other people or organisations. Furthermore, the law also covers people who are only temporarily disabled, or those that may overcome the disability with the help of some specific device (Nelson and Kleiner, 2001).

Many past studies have revealed the effort to discover various employment barriers facing employees with disabilities (Barnes, 2003; Barnes and Mercer, 2005; Roulstone and Warren, 2006). For instance, a study by Goldstone and Meager (2002) done on behalf of the United Kingdom Department for Work and Pensions, explored the employment barriers for people with disabilities where they primarily examined major barriers to employment faced by the them, including employment policies and practices, employers' awareness and attitudes of the Disability Discrimination Act, workplace adjustments for employees with disabilities and employers' attitudes and perceptions towards employees with disabilities. Osman (2003), Chelvi (2007) and Butler (2007) highlight employers' negative attitudes and perceptions towards employees with disabilities on the grounds of their disabilities as one of the major employment barriers faced by them. The attitudes of the individuals with disabilities themselves such as feeling of incompetence also contribute to the low employment rate of people with disabilities.

Reviews

Since 1980 new theories of intelligence have been introduced and are gradually replacing the traditional theory. The whole child has become the centre of education not only his reasoning capacities, but also his creativity, emotions, and interpersonal skills. The Multiple Intelligences theory has been introduced by Howard Gardner (1983), and the Emotional Intelligence theory by BarOn (1985), Mayer and Salovey (1990) and Goleman (1995). IQ alone is no more the measure for success; it only counts for 20%, and the rest goes for Emotional and Social Intelligences, and luck (Goleman, 1995).

Emotional Intelligence: It is being able to monitor our own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this to guide our thinking and actions (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). The emotionally intelligent person is skilled in four areas: Identifying, using, understanding, and regulating emotions (Mayer and Salovey, 1993). According to Goleman (1995) emotional intelligence consists of five

components: Knowing our emotions (self-awareness), managing them, motivating ourselves, recognizing emotions in others (empathy), and handling relationships.

A. Intrapersonal scale

The subcomponents of the Intrapersonal EQ scale include Self-regard, Emotional self-awareness, Assertiveness, Independence, and Self-actualization. The responses to items on the Total Intrapersonal composite scale are indicative of an individual who has good self-understanding and who is achieving well up to this point in his life.

Self-regard: The responses indicate reasonable self-regard and an adequate degree of self-respect and self-confidence.

Emotional self-awareness: The responses suggest highly effective emotional self-awareness and indicate an individual who knows how his feelings and emotions impact on his own opinions, attitudes, and judgments.

Assertiveness: The responses indicate a reasonably good ability to express thoughts, feelings, and emotions.

Independence: The responses indicate an individual who is independent in his thinking and who also has a strong preference to act independently.

Self-actualization: The results indicate an individual who feels reasonably content with his accomplishments and with his ongoing activities and roles.

B. Interpersonal scale

This component of the Total EQ-i scale taps interpersonal capacity and functioning. The subcomponents of the Interpersonal scale include Empathy, Social Responsibility, and Interpersonal Relationship. Most interpersonal situations are handled well and with confidence. Most of the time, the opinions and attitudes of others are understood, and he has the ability to relate to people reasonably well. The score is reflective of someone who is usually responsible, dependable, and functions well in tasks involving making contact with others and cooperation.

Empathy: The responses indicate an individual who has a good awareness, understanding, and appreciation of the feelings of others most of the time.

Social Responsibility: The responses pertaining to the Social Responsibility scale indicate an individual who is cooperative and constructive. People who show social responsibility will be helpful when interacting with others and will actively contribute to the "community at large" (society, the corporation, team, etc.).

Interpersonal Relationship: The responses portray an individual who has above average interpersonal skills. This is the scale that ties most directly to the ability to interact with others. Students who show abilities for interpersonal relationships are able to form agreeable relationships and alliances. This ability supports effective communication and the mutually beneficial exchanges of ideas, feelings, and information.

C. Adaptability scales

This part of EQ-i is composed of the Reality Testing, Flexibility, and Problem Solving Scales and examines how successful one is in coping with environmental demands based on one's ability to effectively size up and deal with problematic situations. The Adaptability component is substantially higher than average.

Reality Testing: The results indicate an individual who has an enhanced ability to evaluate and grasp the correspondence between what he experiences (the "subjective") and the facts/reality (the "objective"). This type of person is often described as realistic, well grounded, and "tuned in" to what's going on around him/her. The results indicate a fairly typical ability to adjust emotions, thoughts, and behaviour in dynamic environments and changing conditions. Like most people, significant changes may be perceived as difficult, but most adjustments are handled adequately.

Flexibility: The results indicate a typical ability to adjust emotions, thoughts, and behaviour in dynamic environments and changing conditions.

Problem Solving: The responses to this scale reflect an effective approach to resolving problems. Students who show some abilities to solve problems probably has a very deliberating style, and are good at defining problems as well as generating and implementing potentially effective solutions.

D. Stress management scale

The Stress management component of EQ-i consists of the Stress Tolerance and Impulse Control Subscales. Both components of this composite scale are above average indicating a calm disposition, lack of impulsivity, and the ability to withstand stress.

Stress tolerance: The results of the Stress tolerance scale indicate an enhanced ability to withstand adverse events and stressful situations. Students who show some stress tolerance are generally able to cope with stress actively and effectively. They are generally calm and rarely gets overly anxious or agitated even when under pressure.

Impulse control: The results indicate effective impulse control ability that suggests an individual who is able to resist or delay impulses, drives, and temptations to act. Students who show a reflexive thinking or control of their impulses are rarely impatient, rarely overreact, or lose control. Proper thought is given to decisions and actions helping to avoid careless or costly mistakes.

E. General mood scales

The subcomponents of this composite scale consist of the Optimism and Happiness subscales. These components of EQ-i: YV measure one's general feeling of contentment and overall outlook on life. High scores on these components indicate a positive outlook that can help bolster oneself and those around. The results indicate an effective use of optimism to help maintain a positive attitude. This characteristic is usually beneficial in handling difficult or stressful situations

Optimism: The results indicate an effective use of optimism to help maintain a positive attitude. This characteristic is usually beneficial in handling difficult or stressful situations.

Happiness: The responses to this scale indicate a person who feels generally satisfied with life. Students who show happiness probably have a happy and pleasant disposition that will help maintain, or perhaps even promote, positive feelings in those around him. A positive atmosphere can help lift spirits and improve overall functioning/performance.

Contains two validity indicators - **Positive impression scale**, which measures the extent to which an individual is trying to present himself or herself in an overly positive light and **Inconsistency index**, which helps detect individuals who are responding haphazardly or in an inconsistent way.

This instrument can be used in clinical settings to assess an individual's general degree of emotional intelligence, potential for emotional health, and present psychological well-being, as well as to help establish clear therapeutic goals and evaluate the success of a therapy or intervention program.

It is ideal for use in educational settings to help school psychologists and professionals identify students whose inability to adequately cope with school demands could lead to dropping out of school and/or the development of emotional and behavioural problems.

Research methodology

This study has been conducted with the respondents who working with differently able in Govt. and Public sectors in Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu. A well structured questionnaire has been prepared with multiple choices and rating scale to measure the employees opinion towards Emotional Intelligence. The researcher sought the cooperation from the employees to fill up the questionnaire. The data were collected from 50 employees who have differently able. After collecting the filled in questionnaire, the data were coded for analysis purpose.

Objectives

- To analyze the differently able employee perceptions towards emotional intelligence.
- To find the impact of demographic variations of differently able employees to determining their emotional intelligence.

Data analysis

The data analysis includes a descriptive and ANOVA analysis of the Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire. Also the researcher pretend to study the demographic characteristics of it and analyse the existing relation between itself, the emotional intelligence and the different intelligences proposed, with the aim of delimiting or not the different theory conceptions.

TABLE 1. SHOWS THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Sl. No.	Emotional intelligence	Mean	SD	Mean rank	Friedman test. Chi-square value and significance	Multiple comparison test
1	Interpersonal skills	53.25	5.55	2.85	355.394	1,4
2	Intrapersonal skills	58.31	8.17	4.43	P<0.001	3,5
3	Stress control	54.47	6.85	3.43		2
4	Adoptability	53.04	4.68	2.66		
5	General mood and manner	55.24	8.27	3.60		

Friedman's test was used to find the most preferred emotional intelligence among differently able employees. The researcher intended to repeatedly measure the respondent once under each emotional intelligence of the employees and hence

Friedman test is used. Therefore, it is a matched - respondents or repeated-measure design among five factors.

H_0 : *Opinion towards emotional intelligence is similar among all the respondents.*

The results of the technique and the chi-square (χ^2) statistic are presented in Table-1. It is found that the $\chi^2 = 355.394$ is significant at 0.001 level. Hence, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. On examination of the mean ranks obtained by each emotional intelligence of the employee, it is seen that interpersonal skills and adoptability is the most important emotional intelligence perceived by the respondents in working environment followed by the second level stress control and general mood and manner, and finally third level importance to intrapersonal skills.

TABLE 2. IMPACT OF DEMOGRAPHIC VARIATIONS OF DIFFERENTLY ABLE EMPLOYEES TO DETERMINING THEIR AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

	Mean	SD	F	p	Post hoc test
AGE					
A. Below 31 Years	3.724	0.323	2.652	0.049	A Vs C, B
B. 31-40 Years	3.524	0.361			
C. 41-50 Years	3.573	0.374			
D. Above 50 Years	3.633	0.409			
EDUCATION					
A. School Level Education	3.594	0.427	3.884	0.004	C, A, D, B Vs E
B. Diploma	3.554	0.305			
C. Under Graduation	3.646	0.359			
D. Post Graduation	3.558	0.353			
E. Professional	3.349	0.350			
EXPERIENCE					
A. Below 6 Years	3.589	0.350	0.983	0.417	
B. 6-10 Years	3.531	0.343			
C. 11-15 Years	3.623	0.402			
D. 16-20 Years	3.546	0.390			
E. Above 20 Years	3.568	0.312			
INCOME					
A. Less than Rs 20000	3.594	0.335	1.172	0.320	
B. Rs 20000 - Rs 40000	3.572	0.367			
C. Rs 40001 - Rs 60000	3.527	0.440			
D. More than Rs 60000	3.778	0.376			

In order to identify how the respondents differ with respect to their demographic characteristics towards emotional intelligence ANOVA was performed. Table 2 shows the ANOVA result along with mean and standard deviation in all respects. The result shows that among the demographic variables taken for the study, age ($F = 2.652$; $p = 0.049$) and education ($F = 3.884$; $p = 0.004$) have significant outcome. Whereas other demographic variables like experience ($F = 0.983$; $p = 0.417$) and income ($F = 1.172$; $p = 0.320$) do not have a significant result.

As far as age is concerned, respondents differ significantly with respect to their opinion towards the emotional intelligence. In order to identify the most influencing group, post hoc Bonferroni multiple comparison test was performed which is shown in last column of the table. On noticing the multiple comparison test result it is observed that the respondents who are in the age group of below 31 years (mean = 3.724; SD = 0.323) category are emotional intelligence compared to the respondents

who are in the age group of 31 to 40 years (mean = 3.524; SD = 0.361) and 41 to 50 years (mean = 3.573; SD = 0.374). Therefore, it is concluded that lower the age group, higher emotional intelligence.

Regarding the educational qualification, respondents differ significantly with respect to their opinion about the emotional intelligence. On comparing the different categories of respondents' education, Post hoc Bonferroni multiple comparison test result shows that the respondents who have completed their professional courses (mean = 3.349; SD = 0.350) are significantly differ from other educational categories namely, under graduation (mean = 3.646; SD = 0.359), post graduation (mean = 3.558; SD = 0.353), school level (mean = 3.554; SD = 0.305) and illiterate (mean = 3.594; SD = 0.427). That is to say, professionally educated respondents are having the low emotional intelligence compared to other categories of the respondents. Hence, it is concluded from the result that when the level of education increases, the emotional intelligence will reduce automatically. It With respect to the experience and income, ANOVA test result show insignificant outcome, which means that the respondents do not differ significantly based on their experience and income towards their opinion about the emotional intelligence.

Discussion

The results of the present study concur with the results of the following studies which indicate no relationship between EI and age factor. Tyagi's (2004) study found that the level of emotional intelligence is independent of age and Jacques (2009) reported that age did not predict emotional intelligence among a sample of 221 employees. Gowdhaman and Murugan (2009) reported in their study that there is no significant impact of locality on the emotional intelligence of sample which overlaps with the results of present study.

Also, with respect to the variable family income, results of the current study is in accordance with the results of the study by Gowdhaman and Murugan (2009) which found that socio-economic status or monthly income does not have any significant effect on emotional intelligence. Similarly, Jacques (2009) reported that socio economic status did not predict emotional intelligence.

ANOVA results revealed that there was no significant difference in the sample's EI scores with reference to type of school attended, parental education and family income. This indicates that these factors did not influence the EI of employee with differently able. This result is contrary to the results of the study done by Rani (2011), which revealed that integrated employee with differently able are emotionally more intelligent than their counterparts. With regard to family income, the result of the current study is supported by the empirical studies conducted by Gowdhaman and Murugan (2009) and Jacques (2009), which showed that socio-economic status or monthly income and experience does not have any significant effect on emotional intelligence among employees with differently able. In contrast to this, the study by Mohanty and Devi (2010) revealed that education positively and significantly affects the interpersonal relationship (a component of EI) of the employees with differently able.

Conclusion

Emotional intelligence has become a matter of concern and a subject of research today, since it has been proved that emotional health is fundamental to manage work environment. Employee with differently able needs to be taught the essential skills of Emotional Intelligence alongside improving them work performance and managing co-workers in work environments. Research findings indicate that personal factors and emotional intelligence skills are important to employees with differently able to

improve their work performance. Though there are a number of factors that influence emotional intelligence, the current study concluded that the emotional intelligence of employees with differently able in work environment is affected by their age and education demographic variables and other variables like income and experience of the respondents do not affect. The study findings revealed that adventitiously employees with differently able scored higher emotional intelligence scale. Hence it is suggested that appropriate measures are to be initiated very early in life, to promote emotional intelligence among those with younger employees. This would help to enhance their psychological and social development and improve their overall personalities. By strengthening inclusion on a broader level, and by providing and creating opportunities for them, the underprivileged can live their lives with dignity.

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